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**QO'L JANGICHILARNING MASHG'ULOT JARAYONIDA MAXSUS
JISMONIY TAYYORGARLIGINI TAHLILI**DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11216654>

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada 16-18 yoshli qo'l jangichilarning mashg'ulot jarayonida maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarligini tahlili haqida nazariy malumotlar bayon etilgan.

Kalif so'zlar: tayyorgarlik, sifatlar takomillashtirish, mashq, harakatli o'yinlar, maxsus, jismoniy tayyorgarligini tahlili

Mamlakatimiz mustaqilikka erishgandan so'ng ko'plab sohalarda katta o'zgarishlar amalga oshirildi. Sport sohasidagi o'zgarishlar, xususan bolalar sportiga juda katta e'tibor berila boshlandi. Chunki yurtni kelajagi mamalakatimizda o'sib kelayotgan yoshlar bilan chambarchas bog'liq ekanligi hammaga ayon. Bunga misol qilib O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2018-yil 5-martdagi PF-5368-son "Jismoniy tarbiya va sport sohasida davlat boshqaruvi tizimini tubdan takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi farmoni Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2020-yil 4-martdagi 122-son "Sport turlari bo'yicha terma jamoalar tarkibiga sportchilarni saralab olish tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi qarorlar va O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining Sh. Mirziyoev tomonidan 2021-yil 5-noyabrdagi "O'zbekiston Respublikasida 2024-yil Parij shahrida (Fransiya) bo'lib o'tadigan XXXIII yozgi Olimpiya va XVII-Paralimpiya o'yinlari dasturlariga kiritilgan sport turlaridan kelib chiqib sport turlarini yanada takomillashtirish va ommalashtirish to'g'risida"gi PQ - 5279 - sonli farmonini ko'rsatish mumkin va boshqa bu sohaga tegishli me'yoriy-huquqiy hujjatlarda aks etgan vazifalarni amalga oshirishga ushbu tadqiqoti muayyan darajada xizmat qiladi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasida jismoniy tarbiya va sportni yanada takomillashtirish va ommalashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida O'zbekiston Respublikasi Pre-

zidentining Farmonida mamlakatda yuksak madaniyatga ega bo'lgan har tomonlama yetuk hamda jismonan sog'lom insonni shakllantirish maqsadida, aholining jismoniy tarbiya va sport sohasida malaka va bilimlarini o'rttirishga qaratilgan ustuvor yo'nalishlarni belgilash, iqtidorli sportchilarni tanlab olish (selektsiya) jarayoniga innovatsion shakllar va usullarni joriy etish maqsadida.

Quyidagilar jismoniy tarbiya va sport tizimini isloh qilishning 2025 yilgacha asosiy yo'nalishlari etib belgilangan:

- jismoniy tarbiya va sport bilan muntazam shug'ullanayotgan aholining
 - umumiy sonini 30 foizgacha, sport tashkilot va muassasalarida shug'ullanayotgan yoshlarning umumiy sonini 20 foizgacha oshirish;
 - davlat sport ta'limi muassasalarida trener va mutaxassislarning sifat
 - tarkibi, xususan oliy ma'lumotli xodimlar sonini bosqichma-bosqich 80 foizgacha yetkazish;
 - joylarda yoshlar orasidan iqtidorli sportchilarni tanlab olish (selektsiya)ning samarali va shaffof to'rt bosqichli – tashkilot-tuman (shahar)-hudud-respublika tizimini ishlab chiqish va joriy etish.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Jismoniy tarbiya va sport vazirligi tizimidagi sport maktablari o'quvchi-sportchilari o'rtasida «Bolalar sport o'yinlari»ni o'tkazish orqali iqtidorli sportchilarni aniqlash va yoshlar terma jamoalariga zaxira yaratish hamda oliy ta'lim muas-

sasalari talabalari o'rtasida «Talabalar sport o'yinlari»ni tashkil etish natijasida talabalarni sport bilan muntazam shug'ullanishga jalb etish ko'zda tutilgan.

Qo'l jangichilarning o'rta va uzoq masofalarga yugurishda yuqori natijalarga erishish sportchining har tomonlama tayyorgarligi darajasi bilan belgilanadi. Biroq yuqori darajadagi tayyorgarlikning har tomonlama rivojlangan, mukammal texnik va taktik tayyorgarligidan tashqari, o'rta va

uzoq masofalarga yuguruvchilar uchun zarur bo'lgan maxsus chidamlilikni o'stirishga e'tibor berishi lozim. Biz bilamizki, qisqa masofalarda yugurishning maksimal tezligini 20 sekunddan ortiq ushlab turish qiyin. Masofa uzaygani sayin yugurish tezligi ham pasayib boradi. Bunda S.A.Vakurov bergan ma'lumot bo'yicha yugurish tezligining pasayish kattaliklarini turli masofalarda turlicha tezlikka ega bo'lishini ko'rsatib o'tish maqsadga muvofiqdir (1-jadval).

1-jadval

S.A.Vakurov bo'yicha 16-18 yoshli qo'l jangichilarning turli masofalarga yugurishning maksimal tezligi

Masofa (m)	Yugurish vaqti (jahon rekordi, daq, sek)	Qo'l jangichilar da yugurish tezligi (m/sek)
100	9.58	10.43
200	19.19	10.4
400	43.18	9.2
800	1:41.01	7.9
1500	3:26.0	7.3
3000	7:20.67	6.8
5000	12:37.47	6.6
10000	26:17.53	6.3
21 097,5	58:55.00	5.96
42 195	2:04:55.0	5.62

16-18 yoshli qo'l jangichilarning o'rta va uzoq masofalarga yugurishda yugurish davomiyligining ortishi tezlikning keskin pasayishi bilan ifodalanadi.

Umumiy chidamlilikni rivojlantiruvchi vosita va usullarining qo'llanishi. Uzoq masofalarga davomli, bir maromda yugurish. Yugurishning bu turida tezlik soatiga 8-12 km gacha yetishi mumkin. Odatda, yugurish organizm uchun yetarlicha kislorod iste'mol qilish sharoitiga o'tadi.

Qo'l jangichilar bir maromda yugurish tayyorgarlik davrining birinchi bosqichida mashg'ulotning asosiy vositalardan sanaladi. Tayyorgarligi turlicha bo'lgan yuguruvchilarda bu turdagi yugurishda tezlikni o'lchab berish tomir urish sur'atini nazorat qilish yordamida amalga oshiriladi. Tomir bir daqiqada 140-160 zarba urganda, yugurish

tezligi optimal sanaladi. Qo'l jangichilarning tayyorgarlik davrida bunday rejimda yugurib o'tiladigan masofalar 10-35 km, ularning davomiyligi esa 45 daqiqadan 2 soatgacha davom etadi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda ommaviy sport musoboqalarda Qo'l jangichilarning o'rta masofalarga yuguruvchilarning tutgan o'rni muximdir, buni yuqorida ta'kidlab o'tilgan ommaviy sport musoboqarlardagi ishtiroki va aholining keng qatlamida sog'lomlashtiruvchi ahamiyatiga egadir. Inson sog'lom turmush tarzini to'g'ri amalga oshirish uchun ixtiyoriy ravishda sport bilan muntazam shug'ullanishi lozim.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2020-yil 4-martdagi 122-son "Sport turlari bo'yicha terma jamoalar

tarkibiga sportchilarni saralab olish tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi qarorlar. Mabuot.uz

2. Kerimov.F.A. Sportda ilmiy tadqiqotlar. Toshkent "Ilmiy-texnika axboroti press nashriyoti" -2021.-68.b;

3. Gazyev N.R., To'ychiyev.T.S. Kurash turlari va uni o'qitish metodikasi (kurash) O'quv qo'llanma. 2023 - yil 16- sentyabr-dagi "33/d" - sonli buyrug'iga asosan B.165.

4. Программа развития детско-юношеского волейбола в Восточно-Казахстанской области на 2016-2020

годы.- Усть-Каменогорск. - 2016.- 94с.

5. Шарафеева А.Б. Физическая подготовка волейболистов.

Методические рекомендации. - Томск. - 2008. -54 с.

6. Холодов Ж.К. Теория и методика физического воспитания и спорта: учеб. пособие для студ. высш. учеб. заведений / Ж.К. Холодов, В.С. Кузнецов. - 5е изд., стер. М.: Издательский центр «Академия», 2007 С. 32-51.